

OPEN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH ASSESSMENT AT SOFIA UNIVERSITY “ST. KLIMENT OHRIDSKI”

FINAL REPORT, AURA PROJECT

Analysis, internal and external recommendations

Institution: Sofia University “St. Kliment Ohridski”

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

What was AURA project about? The AURA project (Advancing Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridski’s Research Assessment Towards Open Research) is a CoARA Boost cascading project aiming to catalyse the integration of Open Science principles and practices into research assessment practices in Bulgaria. The project responds to growing international consensus that traditional, metric-driven research assessment systems are no longer fit for purpose, as they distort research behaviour, reinforce inequalities across disciplines, and fail to capture the full value and societal impacts of research contributions.

What are the current challenges in Bulgaria? AURA operates at the intersection of European research assessment reform efforts and a highly centralised national evaluation system. Bulgaria represents a particularly challenging but informative case: while national legislation and policy have recently advanced significantly in the area of Open Science, research assessment remains dominated by quantitative indicators focused on publication counts, journal prestige, and citation metrics. This applies both to the assessment of individual researchers and institutions.

What institutional case study is at AURA’s core? The project focused on Sofia University “St. Kliment Ohridski” as a flagship national institution and one of the three CoARA signatories in the country. Through legal and policy analysis, institutional review, stakeholder engagement, and comparison with European reform debates, AURA examined where and how Open Science practices could be meaningfully integrated into research assessment without breaching national legal constraints.

What were the main findings of AURA? The findings demonstrate that while systemic reform at the national level requires political commitment and legislative change, there is substantial scope for institutional-level reform, particularly through internal evaluation and attestation procedures. AURA proposes a set of open science–aligned criteria, tools, and processes that can be adopted incrementally, strengthening transparency, quality, and societal relevance of research.

What is the novelty of AURA? Since the topic of open science in the evaluation of scientific research is completely new for the Bulgarian reality, first of all, the activities under AURA helped to introduce the topic at the individual, university, and national levels and to address the needs in the co-creation process, by proposing systems for its introduction mainly through incentives.

Second, two approaches were used to introduce the topic of open science in the research assessment by: 1) engaging researchers by identifying the benefits for their work and easing the administrative obstacles in their attestation, and 2) engaging the senior management of Sofia University “St Kliment Ohridski” to discuss potential changes in the institutional Code of Practice, synchronised with the efforts of COARA.

Third, national institutions such as the Ministry of Education and Science and the National Evaluation and Accreditation Agency were also involved in discussions on applying the principles of open science to the external evaluation of scientific institutions.

Fourth, an informal Advocacy Group for Open Science in Research Assessment was formed to enforce the principles of COARA and to attract universities to sign up.

And fifth, not least, attracting the general public through a campaign to expose the myths about open science and assessment.

What recommendations did AURA make? The report concludes with recommendations for institutional leaders, national policymakers, and CoARA stakeholders, positioning AURA as a transferable pilot for reform in countries with similarly rigid regulatory environments.

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1. INTRODUCTION: RESEARCH ASSESSMENT REFORM AND THE ROLE OF AURA

Research assessment is a key governance mechanism in contemporary research management systems. It shapes how researchers allocate time, choose research questions, collaborate, and communicate results. Over the past two decades, the assessment system in Bulgaria has increasingly relied on quantitative indicators, particularly publication counts, journal impact factors, and citation-based metrics. While such indicators offer apparent objectivity and comparability, they have also generated a wide range of unintended consequences.

Curry et al (2020) define Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) as “an umbrella term for approaches to assessment which incentivise, reflect and reward the plural characteristics of high-quality research, in support of diverse and inclusive research cultures”. One current trend in research assessment is the effort to integrate in a more balanced manner diverse outputs, practices and activities that maximise the quality and impact of research. This requires basing assessment primarily on qualitative judgement, for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators (CoARA 2022).

At the European level, this push for rethinking concerns have led to a coordinated reform movement, crystallised in the establishment of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA). The AURA project contributes to this reform agenda by addressing a specific national and institutional context. Bulgaria combines a highly centralised legal framework for research assessment with emerging Open Science policies that have not yet been fully operationalised in evaluation practices. This creates a tension between progressive policy aspirations and still conservative assessment mechanisms. A widespread research managerial concern is that the move towards new assessment system will cause havoc, but the negative influence of the current assessment system, such as ‘salami publishing’ and forming groups which produce vast numbers of superficially collaborative publications, have neither been explored in detail nor tackled.

AURA was designed to explore how this tension could be addressed pragmatically. Rather than proposing abstract reforms, the project focused on concrete criteria, tools, and processes that could be implemented within existing institutional and legal frameworks, while remaining aligned with CoARA principles and European best practice.

2. METHODOLOGY AND EVIDENCE BASE

The AURA project employed a qualitative, evidence-based mixed methods design to capture legal, institutional, and cultural dimensions of research assessment in Sofia University “St Kliment Ohridski” as a Bulgarian example.

First, a desk research was conducted on European and international literature on research assessment reform, Open Science, and research on research assessment. This provided the conceptual framework for analysing current practices and identifying reform trajectories.

It should be mentioned that the project designed its own AURA framework (see Section 3). While there are various existing frameworks for research assessment, they all reflect different layers of analysis and principles. The absence of a single, universal framework reflects the complexity of research evaluation itself. There are several factors which contribute to the complexity in designing a research assessment framework.

First, research evaluation operates across multiple levels: individuals, teams, institutions, funders, and national systems. Each of those levels has different purposes and constraints. Second, research systems are heterogeneous, and this should be tackled by flexible or multiple coexisting framework mechanisms. Third, evaluation systems embed values, power relations, and incentive structures which are influenced by the existing national and European policies and regulations. Last but not least, the growing emphasis on Open Science, societal engagement, and responsible research has expanded what counts as a valuable research contribution. This diversification makes it neither feasible nor desirable to define a single evaluative template. This aspect is particularly relevant to AURA as it focuses on exploring how open science contributions can be integrated into a system of research assessment which does not include any ORRI dimensions for the time being.

Exploring existing frameworks, we could identify several types of efforts developed in recent years:

- Principles-based frameworks (e.g. CoARA, DORA, Leiden Manifesto)
- Measurement frameworks for system-level analysis (e.g. OECD manuals)
- Context-specific operational models at institutional and national levels

The development of conceptual frameworks tailored to specific purposes and contexts is a good and needed practice. Such frameworks do not compete with existing ones; they typically apply shared principles into locally meaningful evaluation designs.

As an outcome of our exploration of current research on research assessment, we suggest the AURA conceptual framework (see Section 3).

Second, a detailed legal and policy analysis examined the Bulgarian framework governing research assessment, academic career progression, accreditation, and Open Science. Particular attention was paid to recent legislative developments, including the introduction of rights and obligations for secondary publication and the establishment of the Bulgarian Open Science Portal (see Section 4).

Third, institutional practices at Sofia University “St. Kliment Ohridski” were analysed through a review of internal regulations, attestation procedures, and quality assurance mechanisms. (see Section 5).

Fourth, stakeholder engagement activities were organised, including public events, expert discussions, and interactive consultations using digital tools. These activities provided insight into researchers’ perceptions, levels of awareness, and perceived barriers to reform. (see Section 6).

Finally, comparative examples from other European contexts, including the UK REF and discussions emerging from the recent event on research assessment delivered during the Danish EU-level

presidency, were used to situate the Bulgarian case within broader reform dynamics. Bringing them on board helped to provide recommendations (see Section 7).

LIMITATIONS

This study has its limitations. It focuses on one institution, Sofia University “St Kliment Ohridski” and it is not representative in nature but it provides some insights and an emerging picture of an existing consensus of the various stakeholders involved for a reform in the research assessment. Adding the open science dimension is a nice opportunity for fostering this process.

3. FROM STATE OF THE ART IN RESEARCH ON RESEARCH ASSESSMENT TO AURA FRAMEWORK

Research on research assessment has expanded significantly over the past decade but is not yet fully developed; the international initiatives such as the AGORRA project¹ are not yet including Bulgaria in the analysis of research assessment systems.

However, research on research assessment for other environments helps by identifying some valuable insights. A core finding is that heavy reliance on quantitative indicators leads to systematic distortions in the individual research practices. Metric-dominated systems tend to prioritise short-term, low-risk research that can be rapidly published in high-impact journals. They disadvantage disciplines with slower publication cycles, smaller research communities, or stronger local-language orientations, particularly in the social sciences and humanities. The latter finding is fully relevant in Bulgaria where humanities disciplines related to Bulgarian history, language, literature, art are at a disadvantage. Integrating these aspects into research design is essential as it allows to compare the local situation with the findings from other research environments.

AURA CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK: ASSESSING RESEARCH EVALUATION SYSTEMS

The framework is structured around five interdependent dimensions. Together, they allow systematic analysis.

Figure 1. AURA framework

DIMENSION 1: PURPOSE AND VALUES

¹ <https://researchonresearch.org/project/agorra/>

Question: *What is the evaluation framework for?*

Key aspects:

- Explicit goals (**excellence, productivity**, impact, accountability)
- Implicit values (**competition vs collaboration**, speed vs quality)
- Potential for integrating Open Science outcomes and ORRI principles
- Alignment with public interest and societal goals

AURA statement: This framework is intended for institutional use. The key aspects combine the motivation (in the case of Sofia University, the biggest drivers are excellence and productivity, shown in bold, but other institutions could have a different focus, e.g. impact or accountability). The framework explicitly states the values at its core (e.g., integrating assessment components into collaborative research is an essential institutional driver at Sofia University; another value is the balance of speed and quality). The framework also integrates ORRI principles and explores the opportunities for involving open science into research assessment, being also aligned with public interest and societal goals.

DIMENSION 2: OBJECTS OF EVALUATION

Question: *What is being evaluated?*

Levels:

- **Individual researchers**
- Research groups / teams
- Institutions
- Projects or programmes
- Research support services

Outputs and activities:

- Publications
- Projects, collaborations and knowledge transfer
- Data and software
- Integration of research in teaching and learning
- Societal engagement
- Research leadership and service

AURA statement: Within Sofia University, AURA explored the individual research assessment as an initial level of assessment. We are mindful that there are other processes on different levels and a larger reform would require harmonising all the levels. Within these levels, the current situation primarily focuses on publications and projects. We have expanded the outputs and activities with data/software integration of research in teaching, societal engagement, and research leadership and service.

DIMENSION 3: CRITERIA AND INDICATORS

Question: *How is quality defined and evidenced?*

Types:

- Quantitative indicators (counts, citations, rankings)
- Qualitative criteria (peer judgement, narratives)
- Process indicators (openness, reproducibility)
- Contextual indicators (discipline, career stage)

AURA statement: These types of indicators are wider than the currently used, which are mostly in the group of quantitative indicators. The rationale for including them is to explore what are the perceptions and attitudes of the various stakeholders.

DIMENSION 4: PROCESSES AND GOVERNANCE

Question: *How are evaluations conducted and by whom?*

Elements:

- Decision-making structures and workflows
- Degree of institutional autonomy
- Accountability and appeal mechanisms
- Role of peer review vs automated metrics
- Use of external actors (rankings, databases, commercial providers)

AURA statement: The aim of including this component is to map the existing practices, identifying the potential for evolution.

DIMENSION 5: EFFECTS AND CHANGE POTENTIAL

Questions: *What does the system actually do in practice? What is the realistic change direction?*

Aspects to consider:

- Collaboration patterns
- Career trajectories

- Equity across disciplines and groups
- Research agendas
- Publication strategies
- Research integrity and trust

Temporal and environment dimension:

- Short-term behavioural responses
- Long-term cultural change
- Path dependency and lock-in effects

AURA statement: The aim of including this component is to map the existing practices, identifying the potential for evolution.

Cross-cutting themes

Across all five dimensions, two cross-cutting themes are essential to monitor:

1. **Equity, diversity and inclusiveness** (applicability across disciplines, languages, career stages, institutions).
2. **Openness and transparency** (data availability, decision traceability, level of understanding among the various stakeholders)

HOW THE FRAMEWORK IS USED

The framework supports several uses:

- Audit/diagnostic analysis: Identify misalignments between goals, indicators, and effects.
- Comparative assessment: Compare systems across institutions.
- Reform design: Identify leverage points (e.g. criteria vs processes).
- Monitoring and evaluation: Track changes over time without relying solely on metrics.

Its successful application depends on collecting diverse data and using **mixed methods**:

- document analysis
- legal and policy review
- stakeholder consultations
- behavioural evidence
- quantitative data
- altmetrics

Within AURA, it is used for diagnostic analysis which is presented in Section 7.

In the next section, we provide the outcomes of the analysis of the legal framework for research assessment and open science in Bulgaria.

4. LEGAL AND POLICY FRAMEWORKS FOR RESEARCH ASSESSMENT AND OPEN SCIENCE IN BULGARIA

AURA performed an analysis of the national legal frameworks for research assessment and open science (an analytical report had been prepared in Bulgarian and is available upon request; this section summarises its findings). The Bulgarian research system is governed by a dense and highly centralised legal framework. Research assessment criteria are embedded in legislation regulating academic career development, institutional accreditation, and public research funding.

In the recent years there have seen significant progress in the Open Science policy landscape. Strategic documents, national plans, and legislative amendments have introduced explicit commitments to open access, open data, and public availability of publicly funded research outputs. Notably, Bulgaria has introduced both a right and an obligation for secondary publication, strengthening the legal basis for Open Science.

Despite these advances, assessment frameworks have remained largely unchanged. Minimal national requirements for academic progression are based almost exclusively on quantitative indicators linked to publication and citation metrics, with a strong dependence on Web of Science and Scopus. These indicators are legally binding and leave little room for institutional deviation.

AURA team performed analysis of 26 legal documents and projects at the EU and global levels, nine at the national level and 13 at the Sofia University level. The following problems were identified:

- *Problem 1: Lack of generally valid requirements/standards for scientific achievements necessary for acquiring a scientific degree and for holding an academic position.* This led to a significant increase, acceleration and completion of numerous procedures for acquiring a scientific degree and for holding an academic position and, accordingly, to an increase in the number of habilitated persons, without this being linked to an increase in scientific production on an institutional and national scale.
- *Problem 2: Lack of sufficiently strict requirements for professional competence and objectivity of the members of the scientific juries.* This creates opportunities for subjectivism, since uniform rules for the work of scientific juries have not been established, as well as the requirements for the preparation of opinions and reviews by the members of the scientific jury have not been standardized, especially with regard to the scientific achievements of the candidates, including the presence or absence of plagiarism in the scientific works evaluated in the procedures for acquiring scientific degrees and for occupying academic positions in higher education institutions and scientific organizations.
- *Problem 3: Lack of specific mechanisms for effective control,* including by the Minister of Education and Science, in accordance with the Constitution and the reasons for the decision of the Constitutional Court of 2010, over the procedures during their conduct and after their completion.
- *Problem 4: Lack of a legally defined mechanism in the legal framework on research to counteract the manifestations of plagiarism among the academic community after the*

repeal of the Law on Scientific Degrees and Scientific Titles in 2010, which cannot be compensated by the regulation existing in the Law on Copyright and Related Rights and in the Criminal Code. According to the reasons, it is necessary to create a special regulation for the purposes of academic development, which would cover all hypotheses of plagiarism among the academic community, such as cases of borrowing from an unknown author on the Internet, which is becoming an increasingly growing practice according to the signals received by the institutions.

- *Problem 5: The principles of the European Charter for Researchers, the Code of Conduct for the Selection of Researchers and the Code of Ethics for Scientists are still not applied in higher education institutions and scientific organizations, which is a requirement of the Updated National Strategy for the Development of Scientific Research in the Republic of Bulgaria 2017-2030, adopted by a decision of the National Assembly.*

This analysis is helpful in identifying several problems, mostly caused by misalignment of different legal acts, which impact research assessment.

Open science, although declared an underlying principle within research, has not been properly integrated into the national legislation which defines the institutional regulations – this is a key area which needs a combined national and institutional reform.

The analysis shows a clear misalignment between Open Science policy objectives and research assessment mechanisms. While researchers are increasingly encouraged, and in some cases required, to make outputs openly available, these practices are not systematically recognised or rewarded in evaluation processes.

This structural disconnect limits the transformative potential of Open Science and reinforces conservative research behaviours. At the same time, the legal framework does allow limited flexibility at institutional level, particularly in internal evaluation and attestation procedures.

5. INSTITUTIONAL PRACTICES AT SOFIA UNIVERSITY ST. KLIMENT OHRIDSKI

Sofia University “St. Kliment Ohridski” operates within the national legal framework but retains autonomy in organising internal quality assurance and evaluation procedures. This autonomy is most visible in periodic attestation of academic staff, which complements national criteria for career progression.

Analysis of institutional practices shows that publication-based indicators remain dominant. However, attestation procedures are less rigid than national requirements and allow for contextual interpretation of research contributions. This creates an opportunity to introduce Open Science aligned criteria without undermining compliance with national law.

Stakeholder engagement conducted during the AURA project revealed mixed levels of awareness and support for reform. While many researchers recognise the limitations of current assessment practices, concerns remain about competitiveness, fairness, and international recognition.

Importantly, institutional leaders expressed interest in incremental reform approaches that would enhance quality and transparency without exposing researchers to additional risk. This reinforces the strategic importance of focusing on internal procedures as a first step towards broader reform.

One area of particular interest is how to support a culture of collaboration and how to provide a fair evaluation of the inputs of team members.

A summary of the key themes emerging from the stakeholder analysis is presented in Appendix 1, complemented by a 'secret client' study summarised in Appendix 2.

6. KEY FINDINGS: STAKEHOLDERS' PERCEPTIONS

AURA organised a series of capacity building events and a final event which brought all key national stakeholders (Ministry of Education and Science, the National Evaluation and Accreditation Agency, the Liaison Office of Bulgaria at the EC) and high-level representatives of Sofia University "St Kliment Ohridski" and other research performing organisations and non-governmental sector on 11 December 2025.

At this event, the AURA team collected feedback on a number of issues around research assessment.

While the results which are shared do not have a statistically significant result, they show a clear and strong consensus on the need to move in the direction of research assessment reform (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Stakeholder responses: is there a need for reform, 11 December 2025.

Figure 3. Stakeholder responses: open science metrics in research assessment, 11 December 2025.

There is also a strong positive opinion on the importance of integrating open science metrics in the research assessment (see Fig. 3). However, the respondents' opinions where should a reform start: from the individual assessment, the institutional assessments or coordinated on both levels, show diverse views (see Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Stakeholder responses: institutional vs individual assessment, 11 December 2025.

The question on the biggest challenges to a reform in the research assessment in Bulgaria shows that the complexity of the reform and the publication ecosystems are the biggest concerns (see Fig. 5). There is also a predominant positive response to the question if Bulgaria should engage stronger with CoARA (see Fig. 6).

What are the biggest challenges to implementing research assessment reform in Bulgaria?

Figure 5. Stakeholder responses: challenges to reforming research assessment, 11 December 2025.

Figure 6. Stakeholder responses: expanding Bulgarian presence in CoARA, 11 December 2025.

The AURA project identified several interrelated barriers to integrating Open Science into research assessment. These include the rigidity of national legal requirements, strong dependence on commercial bibliometric databases, limited awareness of Open Science among researchers, and institutional risk aversion.

At the same time, a number of enabling factors were identified. Recent legislative reforms provide a solid legal foundation for Open Science. Institutional autonomy in internal evaluation creates

space for experimentation. European-level initiatives, including CoARA, offer legitimacy and shared direction.

Crucially, the findings suggest that reform does not need to be comprehensive or immediate to be effective. Incremental changes at institutional level can generate learning, build confidence, and create evidence for future national reform.

7. DEVELOPING RESEARCH ASSESSMENT CRITERIA, TOOLS, AND PROCESSES

Based on the evidence gathered, AURA proposes a pragmatic approach to developing Open Science–aligned assessment criteria. Rather than replacing existing metrics, the project advocates complementing them with qualitative and process-oriented indicators.

Proposed criteria include mandatory open accessibility of assessed research outputs, recognition of data sharing and stewardship, narrative descriptions of research contribution and impact, and acknowledgement of team-based and interdisciplinary work.

These criteria can be embedded in existing processes, particularly attestation, without altering national minimal requirements. Tools such as structured narrative templates and institutional repositories can support consistent implementation.

The emphasis is on feasibility, transparency, and alignment with both CoARA principles and national legal obligations.

Applying the AURA framework to Sofia University, we can provide the following succinct description of the current situation.

Figure 7. AURA framework in the case of Sofia University

8. RECOMMENDATIONS

AURA proposes the following recommendations on refreshing the institutional Code of practice and the Law for the development of academic staff.

INTERNAL RECOMMENDATIONS

At the institutional level, AURA recommends:

- Revising the attestation procedures to explicitly include Open Science practices, requiring open availability of assessed outputs, and providing guidance and support to researchers. The practices which need to be reflected are publications in open access (visible on the Bulgarian portal for open science), open datasets deposited to institutional or discipline-specific repositories, open software and citizen science involvement. These internal procedures can be adjusted on faculty level which also would support the diversification and inclusivity in fair assessment which captures the discipline-specific aspects. These revisions also should suggest a best practice approach in documenting contributions of co-authors and project teams.
- Strengthening the contribution to CoARA. While Sofia University is a signatory of CoARA, AURA also recommends more proactive contribution to working groups and the delivery of an institutional code of practice as steps which will consolidate and strengthen the institutional effort.
- The reform can grow from faculty level to institutional level – this would mean incentivising more faculties to revise the individual assessment processes and criteria.

EXTERNAL RECOMMENDATIONS

- National level
 - Reviewing the minimal national requirements to reduce over-reliance on narrow quantitative indicators and to recognise Open Science contributions.
 - The national policies can address some of the prevailing national practices in research assessment, namely, primary reliance on publications, dependance on WoS & Scopus ranking, use of mostly quantitative metrics, lack of flexibility and appropriate integration of the domain-specific aspects.
 - As internal individual assessment seems most feasible, the national policy can support more institutions to rething this research assessment component.
 - Bulgaria needs more support for sharing research data – this is a particularly underdeveloped open science component. One incentive could be including open data sharing as an indicator in the research assessment of individuals.
- At CoARA level, AURA highlights the need for continued support for institutions operating under rigid legal frameworks and for sharing evidence from pilot projects.

9. CONCLUSIONS

AURA demonstrates that meaningful progress in research assessment reform is possible even in constrained legal environments. By focusing on institutional processes and aligning with European reform agendas, the project provides a realistic and transferable model.

The integration of Open Science into research assessment should be understood not as an administrative burden, but as a pathway to higher quality, greater transparency, and stronger societal relevance of research.

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APPENDIX 1. STAKEHOLDERS' ATTITUDES TOWARDS OPEN SCIENCE

The emerging findings and recommendations on key aspects related to open science and research assessment are summarised in the following table. For the time being, we are unpacking components which are relevant to three types of stakeholders – researchers/academics, University management and the general public.

Themes	Researchers	University Management	Public	Recommendations
1. Awareness of Open Science & Research Assessment Principles	<p>Researchers show a high level of awareness (92.6%) about Open Research, mainly through experiences with open-access publications, open data, and educational resources. However, only a small fraction fully embrace the broader UNESCO definition of Open Research and its comprehensive elements.</p> <p>Responsible Research is less of a local priority compared to Open Research.</p>	<p>University administrators, as well as managers of Open Research Infrastructures demonstrate the highest level of understanding of Open Research in its entirety, as they are directly involved in policy-making and regulatory frameworks. However, they face difficulties in effectively communicating policies to researchers and the public.</p> <p>There is a PhD School, and it could serve as a good communication channel to distribute knowledge for OS - there are some initial signs of courses developed for PhD students.</p>	<p>Citizens and NGOs perceive ORRI as accessible, understandable, and beneficial to daily life. However, their understanding is still fragmented, associating Open Research primarily with open-access publications and communication of scientific results. Citizens are also very confident they can contribute to research even without researchers' guidance.</p> <p>Limited knowledge of Citizens Science (CS)</p> <p>Citizens mostly used as data providers but not contributing to formulating research and analysing the results.</p>	<p>Targeted campaigns for early-stage and experienced researchers to promote open science and the opportunities it offers for scientific and career development.</p>
2. Open Science Incentives	<p>There are no formal requirements in</p>	<p>There is a Law and secondary legislation, but the</p>	<p>NGOs collaborate on projects with academics, but</p>	<p>Setting minimum requirements and a broad system of</p>

	<p>the department to publish open access, share data, or engage in citizen science, unless it is a requirement on the EU projects.</p>	<p>documents and procedures have not aligned yet.</p>	<p>this is a relatively small part of the researchers' assessment. not formal procedures of the ass at the University. There are many initiatives. Beautiful Science, Ratio, etc.</p>	<p>incentives for the assessment system (both on national and institutional level).</p> <p>Co-creation process for OS requirements and incentives.</p>
<p>3. Motivation and Culture related to Research Assessment</p>	<p>Targeting influential journals for papers</p> <p>High dependencies of the publishers</p> <p>The motivation is based on enthusiasts, who are a limited number in the natural and mathematical disciplines, but are highly committed and pioneers in the field.</p> <p>Early-stage scientists are also motivated because they believe this is a good way to advance their careers.</p> <p>For the most part, scientists believe that open science activities are often</p>	<p>The University administration is conservative, rigid and relies on quantitative metrics because they are easily measurable, provable and non-biased.</p> <p>They have no motivation to introduce innovations if it is not a legal obligation, and yet there is a delay.</p> <p>Balance between commercialisation and public good</p> <p>University Ratings</p>	<p>There is a need for more scientific knowledge to refute fake news and disinformation.</p>	<p>Formalise the process through a bonus system for researchers, faculty, and universities, which is tied to specific financial incentives, additional material incentives, and awards.</p> <p>Recognise the contribution of scientists implementing open science through awards, specialisations, and the like.</p>

	<p>solitary, time-consuming, and do not yield quick or short-term benefits, both material and in terms of a scientific career.</p> <p>They fear that by publishing, their results and data will be stolen.</p>			
4. Support & Infrastructures	<p>Discussions exposed the strengths and weaknesses of the process – infrastructures are often lacking or not user friendly (difficult deposit of publications, complicated extraction of data on citations).</p> <p>Incentives that directly influence evaluation and career development, but not as an obligation, but as a bonus</p>	<p>There is a lack of an up-to-date green access university repository where researchers can upload their work. (there is an older installation which is currently out of use and other systems which capture publication details but not the actual publications).</p> <p>No unit would be responsible for horizontally coordinating the processes of open science at the University.</p>	<p>They have no information about what exactly citizen science is, despite having experience with such practices.</p> <p>There is no funding for such projects.</p> <p>There is no network of similar organisations from different scientific disciplines.</p>	<p>Infrastructures to support the process – university repository</p> <p>Creating an open science structure that monitors the implementation of the principles in the evaluation and attestation system.</p> <p>Citizen Science Platform</p>
5. Activities	<p>Joint discussion of the new criteria for open science, not to be imposed from above as an obligation, but rather as a bonus.</p> <p>Seminars, trainings, and mentoring on the</p>	<p>The problem of plagiarism is a serious issue that could be addressed through Open Peer Review.</p> <p>AI abuse</p>	<p>There is no place, event, or festival where you can meet, learn more, and share experiences.</p>	<p>Introducing bonus points for implementing open science in the researcher's attestation card.</p> <p>Developing programs to stimulate open science - awards,</p>

	individual principles and how they bring concrete benefits for their scientific and career development.	Winning EU projects is directly dependent on data sharing. Enhancing the skills of academic staff leads to improved results and higher rankings for universities.		points, credits, mentoring, training courses.
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Researchers have a range of concerns around the way evaluation is made and it is clear open research still needs to be better integrated and positioned within research practice. Currently it does not contribute to assessment practice.

In the next months we will be offering possible scenarios for including open research in various assessment processes.

APPENDIX 2. SUMMARY OF THE SILENT CLIENT STUDY

The Silent Client study was conducted with the Department of Projects and Science of Sofia University. This unit is responsible for tracking all submitted project proposals as well as supporting successful ones and deals with a wide range of donors with different requirements. The calls of Horizon are those with the most apparent demand and an allocated part of the submission forms to discuss open science. In the cases of national funding, this is just starting.

The following underdeveloped areas were identified:

- The relatively low knowledge of the concept of open science impacts the project planning where this component is either not taken into consideration or follows the lead of larger consortia in the case of Horizon projects.
- Evaluation is done retrospectively, after a project is finalised.
- When preparing project proposals, there is no connection between the evaluation of scientists and the design of the project. There is a criterion in the academic assessment which takes into consideration the amount of external funding they secured but there is nothing related to the efforts to design proposals and the open science components in those proposals.
- Good practices are mostly emerging when project proposals are discussed, which allows for an entry point to engage researchers.

This study mostly captures the perceptions of units which play a key role in supporting researchers. As they also are relevant to providing guidance on project opportunities, it is useful to establish how such a unit communicates aspects related to research assessment in relation to project work.

Research support offices are one of the university structures which could improve the connection between project work in particular – especially having in mind the various open research requirements of different funders. This is still an underused opportunity to expand the knowledge on opens science across researchers.

In the next months of the project, our team will explore how research offices can provide more robust guidance on open science.